

Working Statement Method

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Retrieval of diving lead weights lost by recreational divers in the mesophotic zone of a highly touristic coral reef drop-off near Sharm-el-Sheikh (Egypt): the case of the Ras Mohammed National Park

with a parallel focus on the black coral fauna (Hexacorallia: Antipatharia)

ABSD Training – Sharm-el-Sheikh 2023

Red Sea, Egypt

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This document has been read and approved by all the participants of the mission.

Signatures

1. Background of the “Advanced Belgian Scientific Diver” Training

The certifications of Scientific Divers are occupational certifications allowing the use of open circuit scuba diving or rebreather to accomplish scientific underwater tasks. It is meant for professional scientists, university students or researchers and personnel of scientific institutions that need to dive to carry out their work. Scientific diving is regulated by law in many countries in Europe. In Belgium, a Royal Decree (Royal Decree of 28 April 2017 on the protection of workers against the risks associated with work in hyperbaric environments) imposes a specific training to be authorised to work under pressure. The training is divided in two parts: the BSD (Belgian Scientific Diver) and the ABSD (Advanced Belgian Scientific Diver), which are taught by BELSPO (Belgian Science Policy Office), the only training agency recognized by the PS Employment, Labour and Social Dialogue. It is managed by the Working Group on Scientific Diving (BWGSD) which delivers the professional competency as described in the Royal Decree.

At the international level, the BWGSD is a member of the European Scientific Diving Panel (ESDP) of the Marine Research Institute and Station (MARS) network. This means that the Belgian certifications are equivalent to European Scientific Diver and Advanced European Scientific Diver certifications, which are European competencies for scientific diving at work. The certifications are valid for 5 years and proof of a certain number of dives (including scientific dives) are mandatory for renewal. Renewal procedure involves the justification of 60 dives including 30 scientific dives and CPR certification not older than 2 years (both first aid and O₂ provider), with an additional 5 dive activities at ABSD level in the past 5 years and 1 in the past year for ABSD certifications. The ABS divers can lead and organise diving operations following the law.

Divers who want to access the ABSD has to hold a valid BSD certification and fulfil a series of prerequisites which are listed below:

THEORY

1. diving physics and physiology, the causes and effects of diving related illnesses and disorders and their management.
2. the specific problems associated with diving to and beyond 30m, calculations of air requirements, correct use of decompression tables.
3. equipment, including personal dive computers and guidelines as to their safe use.
4. emergency procedures and diving casualty management.
5. the principles and practice of dive planning and the selection and assessment of divers.
6. legal aspects and responsibilities relevant to scientific diving in Europe and elsewhere.
7. dive project planning.

DIVE MANAGEMENT

1. diving first aid, including CPR and oxygen administration to diving casualties.
2. SCUBA rescue techniques and management of casualties.
3. the use and user maintenance of appropriate SCUBA diving equipment, including dry suits and full face masks.
4. basic small boat handling, and electronic navigation.
5. supervision of diving operations.

IN-WATER SKILLS

1. search methods, such as those utilising free swimming and towed divers together with remote methods suitable for a various range of surface and subsurface situations.
2. survey methods, both surface and sub-surface, capable of accurately locating and marking objects and sites.
3. the basic use of airbags and airlifts for controlled lifts, excavations and sampling.

4. basic rigging and rope work, including the construction and deployment of transects and search grids.
5. underwater navigation methods using suitable techniques.
6. recording techniques.
7. roped/tethered diver techniques and various types of underwater communication systems such as those utilising visual, aural, physical and electronic methods.
8. sampling techniques appropriate to the scientific discipline being pursued.

DIVING EXPERIENCE

100 dives, of which:

1. 50 dives with a scientific task of work, such as listed above.
2. 10 dives between 20m and 29m.
3. 10 dives between 29m and 40m or the national limit.
4. 12 dives in the last 12 months, including at least 6 with a scientific task of work.
5. 20 dives in adverse conditions, such as currents, cold water, or moving water.
6. 20 dives as an in-water dive leader.

In addition, ABSD candidates need to write a Working Method Statement focusing on a specific task that has to be accomplished during the training. In this case, the project aims at retrieving diving lead weights lost by recreational divers in a highly touristic place of the Red Sea: the drop-offs of the Ras Mohamed coral reefs. The drop-offs are reaching depths of 100 m, and it is expected to find diving weights in the mesophotic zone between 60 and 100 m depth. In parallel, it is planned to accomplish several tasks related to the black corals (Hexacorallia: Antipatharia) in dive sites around Sharm-el-Sheikh. For instance, this may include transects related to the diversity and abundance of black corals, or fish census of the species found on/near black coral populations.

2. Purpose of this document

This Working Method Statement (WMS) aims to describe the general procedures for the diving operations planned in the framework of the ABSD project mentioned above. This description covers the main points of attention required to ensure that the scientific diving activities necessary to achieve the project's specific objectives are carried out efficiently and safely. The WMS includes:

- A description of the scientific tasks and of the associated material to be used;
- A description of the working area with all preliminary information available in terms of geography and bathymetry;
- A description of the dive platform and the equipment available onboard for communication, navigation, safety and diving logistics;
- A presentation of the diving team including their affiliation, their planned mission onboard, their detailed dive experience and their first aid capacities;
- A description of the administrative requirements including insurances and employers' obligations;
- A description of the logistics for the provision of breathing gas, and of the procedures applied to ensure the good quality of this gas;
- A description of the procedures to manage the saturation and the decompression of divers throughout the mission;
- A detailed risk analysis that:
 - A) Describes how a typical dive will be operated during the mission;

- B) Identifies all foreseen risks associated to the diving operations planned in the area of interest onboard of the diving platform available, with for each of them specific measures to mitigate or eliminate these risks;
- C) Lists all necessary diving & safety equipment;
- D) Details the emergency plan covering the immediate rescue of endangered divers, the primary care to apply to an injured diver and the evacuation procedure in case of emergency;

This working method statement ensures compliance with Article 5 of the Royal Decree of 28 April 2017 on the protection of workers against the risks associated with work in hyperbaric environments. The WMS, including the associated Operational Risk Management (ORM), has to be read and approved by participants.

3. List of scientific tasks foreseen in the water

The Red Sea is famous for its diving spots, especially in the Sharm el-Sheik area and nearby. The high concentration of scuba-divers, either recreational or technical, can have negative effects on marine life. For instance, Dahab (Red Sea), is subject to intensive SCUBA diving, and is one of the world's most dived sites (>30 000 dives/year). As a consequence, it shows a significantly higher number of broken and damaged corals and significantly lower coral cover, as well as an increase in sedimentation rates in entrance points of the dives¹.

Among damages caused by diving activities, we can cite fins touching corals, divers grabbing the reef or touching wildlife, but also pollution due to boat traffic (fuel, waste, sound pollution, ...), or even lost equipment at sea. Lost equipment at sea is a frequent situation, and one of the main objects lost is lead diving weights, as this is generally a piece of equipment that the divers release and pass to the RIB/boat before climbing into the boat. But as soon as a diver releases his buckle/belt, or their weight pockets, the weight is suddenly supported only by their hand and at this time it can be lost and sunk to the depths. In the case of shallow reefs, or in the case of a mooring at 5-10m, it can be envisaged to directly go down to retrieve it; but on some areas, such as in the drop-off walls of Ras Mohammed National Park, the leads can sink in deep places, between 50 and 100m, which are then considered definitively lost.

As the time passes, and thousands of divers succeed each other throughout time, these lost leads may accumulate in the deep. This has several consequences, both economical and ecological.

Economical consequences are directly supported by the clients who lost the gear. Divers do not travel with their own weights as it is not authorised by airline companies, and this is part of the equipment that the dive centres provide to their clients at no cost. In remote places or some countries, dive lead weights can cost a significant price, more than in Europe. Therefore, the loss of dozens of kilograms per year for a dive centre can become a significant loss of money at the end of the year.

From an ecological point of view, losing weight causes different problems. The first is when the weight touches the substrate: it can break corals, and damage or kill wildlife at the moment of impact. The second is linked to the nature of lead which is a toxic compound for marine life. Lead is interesting for diving as it is dense with 11 350 kg/m³, meaning that a weight of 1 kilogram is relatively small. Although it is the least

¹ Hasler, H., & Ott, J. A. (2008). Diving down the reefs? Intensive diving tourism threatens the reefs of the northern Red Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 56(10), 1788-1794.

expensive dense material available, it is a toxic substance that can be a hazard for life. In humans, exposure to lead can damage the nervous system. Lead has a low solubility in water, and pure lead corrodes slowly in the sea. However, corrosion still happens with time and can become a hazard when dozens or hundreds of weights are accumulating in the same zone. It has already been shown that corals can incorporate lead by the result of dissolved metal absorption, included particulate material absorbed by coral tissue or coral feeding².

Nowadays, many shops sell coated weights that protect the inside, but raw weights are still very common worldwide. Other than toxicity, this is marine pollution damaging pristine sites.

This is why it is planned to retrieve lead weights lost by scuba-divers in a drop-off wall of Ras Mohammed during the ABSD training. It is expected to find the weights between 50–100m. This may serve as a pilot study for larger scale projects.

As the area is not known by the candidate, a first dive might be necessary to locate the weights and visualise the topography of the site. After a recognition dive, a good briefing with an adequate decompression procedure (see next chapters) might be discussed between the divers. The plan should consider the gear available, which will be a 100 kg lift-bag. But the way to gather the weights prior to sending them to the surface with the lift-bag has to be discussed once in Egypt depending on the gear available. **The weights are generally found with the belt, and the belts are attached to the lift bag.**

Prior to the task, the role of each diver has to be determined: who will carry the equipment to the bottom, who will operate the lift bag, who will attach the weights, ...

The stage used to inflate the lift bag could be carried by a diver as a bailout with specific marker to signal that this is a piece of scientific equipment, while the lift bag would be stored folded, taking care to not keep air trapped inside from the surface, and then un-clipped and connected to the lift bag once reached the targeted depth. This has the advantage of not having a bulky material to go down to the bottom. On the other hand, the connection between the lift-bag and the tank can also be made in advance prior to the dive, so there is only the tank to open to fill the bag once at depth, with the lift bag attached around the tank using a bungee for instance. This has to be defined between members of the team prior to the dive and according to the easiest way to proceed. Following a logical order, after the recognition dive, the divers would go on the same site and start gathering weights at the deepest point, and then ascent and continue to collect weights along the drop-off until max time to surface (see deco procedures in the next chapters) or capacity of the ned/collection device is reached. In this case, the lift-bag has to be perfectly controlled to ascend with the divers at the same speed.

In any case, the lift-bag should be operated at depth with a specific tank to fill it, for instance:

- At 50m the inflation of 100L lift-bag would use maximum 600L
- At 75m the inflation of 100L lift-bag would use maximum 850L
- At 100m the inflation of 100L lift-bag would use maximum 1100L

Therefore, a 7L Alu tank filled with 200bar of air only dedicated to the lift bag would be enough for the deepest dive planned at 100m, but S80 are available at the dive centre for this purpose. The divers will take care to manipulate inflation and dump valves accordingly.

² Al-Rousan SA, Al-Shloul RN, Al-Horani FA, Abu-Hilal AH (2007) Heavy metal contents in growth bands of Porites corals: record of anthropogenic and human developments from the Jordanian Gulf of Aqaba. Mar Pollut Bull 24(12):1912–1922

Dives between 50 and 100m will involve long decompression procedures (runtimes between 90 and 180 min probably). Therefore, once the scientific task is accomplished, it might be hazardous to ascend with the lift-bag during the whole decompression phase. It is suggested to let it go to the surface and float, before being recovered by surface support from the RIB/or boat (after a good briefing). Divers have to secure the connection between the net/bag with the weights, and the liftbag. This will minimise the risk, as the diver may just have to turn on the valve, let it inflate the bag, and then just release everything including the tank (as long as it is secured to the lift bag).

In parallel to the retrieval of the dive leads, it might be possible to focus on black corals of this area. One possibility is to make transects at different depths to see if there is a difference in the taxonomic assemblage following a depth gradient from shallow to mesophotic depths. It is almost impossible to identify black corals underwater without a thorough analysis of their skeleton under scanning electron microscope, therefore most likely the identification of the antipatharians will be limited to the genera or the family. In shallow/mesophotic waters of the Red Sea, the three most representend families are Antipathidae, Myriopathidae and Aphanipathidae. Black corals can also be sorted by morphotype (whips versus branched versus bottle-brush shaped versus...). The most common genera are *Antipathes*, *Cirrhopathes*, *Stichopathes*, *Cupressopathes*, *Myriopathes*, and *Aphanipathes*. Members of the Myriopathidae are only distinguished based on the structure, number and size of their ramifications.

Transects could be belt-transects where divers deploy a decametre over a distance of 50m, with controlled depth if the substrate allows it, and along which every black coral found in a 2m wide zone is photographed, filmed or noted on a slate. If it is not a squared dive, the depth should be noted along the transect. Another information that can be retrieved is the size-frequency distributions of the antipatharians within the transects. To do so, the divers would have a small PVC stick with tape labels every 10 cm marked with permanent marker, and by placing the stick next to the colony so the divers can write the size (see example in Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The ABSD Candidate, Dr. Lucas TERRANA (on the right) is measuring the height of the colonies of *Antipathella wollastoni* in the mesophotic waters of the Canary Islands along a transect made at 60m depth. Photo credit Franck GAZZOLA – Under The Pole.

4. Working area

The ABSD will take place in Sharm-el-Sheikh, in the Red Sea (Egypt, Fig. 1). This is a highly touristic place, especially for recreational and technical scuba diving agencies. It has a strategic location, at the corner between the Red Sea, the Gulf of Suez and the Gulf of Aqaba. It has a warm desertic climate, hot and dry. Air temperatures reach 40°C in summer and mean annual temperature is 25.1°C, with almost no precipitation (around 10 mm/year). In December, when ABSD training is expected, the average air temperature is around 18°C, while average water temperature is around 25 ° (min. 23.7°C, max. 25.6°C, data source climate-data.org).

Sharm-el-Sheikh is ideally located for scuba-diving, as it has easy access to numerous dive sites around the tip of South Sinai Peninsula. Dive sites are inside three national parks: Ras Mohammed, Tiran and Nabq. Among them, we can cite the most famous such as the wreck SS Thistlegorm, Shark & Yolanda Reef, or Jackson Reef for instance. The Sharm-el-Sheikh marine area is protected and dive centres operate under environmental-friendly procedures. There is a wealth of drop-offs, coral gardens and a very rich fauna including hard and soft corals, turtles, dolphins, mantas and moray eels, hammerheads, pelagic sharks, etc. . . . Diving in Sharm-el-Sheikh is performed by boat or from shore, as the coast is lined by fringing or barrier reefs. The Ras Mohammed National Park access is authorised upon payment of an entrance fee (payable directly to the dive centre, price around 10€/trip). Some dive sites may have strict specific rules (see for instance the rules delivered by the CDWS for diving on the SS Thistlegorm, where guidelines are given for mooring and diving).

The program and the sites are chosen by the skipper and the staff of the local dive centre (see below), according to the weather and to the level of the divers present onboard. This way, it is not possible to give exact coordinates and depth in advance. A complete detailed list of dive sites with their coordinates can be found in <https://www.cdws.travel/divesites>, which is the website of the Chamber of Diving and Water Sports of Egypt (CDWS). The CDWS is a non-profit organisation founded by Egypt's Ministry of Tourism in 2007, with a goal to improve quality, safety and standard of services in the diving and water sports industry, as well as to preserve the unique environment of the Red Sea. Some regulations related to diving activities cited later in this document will directly come from the CDWS. However, scientific divers are expected to dive in warm coral reef environments (~25°C), from shallow to mesophotic areas (0–100 m), with possibly the presence of wrecks. Therefore, they should gear up according to these types of dives (see below for a detailed list of the equipment). Table 1 below regroups dive sites from Ras Mohammed National Park, Tiran Straits and local dive sites in sharm-El-Sheikh (Fig. 2). Please note that depths given in Table 1 are informative and mostly based on recreational depths. Numerous sites are deeper (50–>100m).

Figure 2. A. Sharm-el-Sheikh (red dot) is located at the tip of the South Sinai Peninsula, in the north of the Red Sea. B. The three potential areas where dives will occur.

5. Dive centre and local regulations related to scuba diving activities

Diving activities will be supported and led by the diving centre “CIRCLE DIVERS” (Mobile: +201000608497, <https://www.circledivers.com/>) located in Ras Umm Sid, Badawia Hotel, Al Ferouseya, South Sinai Governorate 46619 (Fig. 3). The centre is a member of the CDWS, meaning that they are operating in accordance with the EN 14467 / ISO 24803 for recreational diving providers. This defines the services relating to training, diving (organised and guided for certified divers) and the hire of diving equipment, required of service providers in the field of recreational scuba diving.

The jetty is 10 minutes away from the centre. It is a centre which organises both recreational and technical dives. They pick the divers up and bring them back after the daily trip to the dive sites. The centre is equipped with freshwater basins to wash the diving gear and hang it afterwards. They provide S80 Alu tanks with DIN exits for recreational diving. Nitrox is free of charge to certified divers. The boat of the centre navigates to Ras Mohammed, the Tiran Strait and the local dive sites as shown in Fig. 2 or Table 1.

Table 1. List of common dive sites near Sharm-el-Sheikh and their coordinates. Depth is given for information but might be deeper on some sites.

Dive site	GPS	Depth (m)
Sharm-el-Sheikh local dive sites		
Amphoras	27° 51' 57 "N ,34° 19' 24 "E	170
Far Garden	27° 54' 55 "N ,34° 21' 31 "E	21
Fiddle Garden	27° 54' 56 "N ,34° 21' 27 "E	20
Middle Garden	27° 54' 52 "N ,34° 21' 8 "E	25
Near Garden	27° 54' 24 "N ,34° 20' 49 "E	20
Paradise	27° 51' 20 "N ,34° 19' 9 "E	30
Pinky Wall	27° 52' 14 "N ,34° 19' 23 "E	180
Ras Bob	27° 57' 47 "N ,34° 24' 39 "E	15
Ras Ghamila	27° 58' 20 "N ,34° 25' 41 "E	15
Ras Katy	27° 50' 50 "N ,34° 18' 6 "E	70
Ras Nasrani	27° 57' 48 "N ,34° 24' 56 "E	>60
Ras Umm Sid	27° 50' 49 "N ,34° 18' 49 "E	70
Shark's Bay	27° 57' 4 "N ,37° 23' 5 "E	20
Sodfa	27° 53' 0 "N ,34° 19' 43 "E	22
Temple	27° 51' 0 "N ,34° 18' 36 "E	30
Tiger Bay	27° 55' 27 "N ,37° 22' 6 "E	27
Tower	27° 52' 56 "N ,34° 19' 32 "E	>100
Turtle Bay	27° 51' 44 "N ,34° 19' 13 "E	26
White Knight	27° 57' 37 "N ,34° 23' 53 "E	35
Ras Mohammed National Park		
Eel Garden	27° 45' 54 "N ,34° 15' 11 "E	18
Jackfish Alley	27° 46' 0 "N ,34° 15' 24 "E	20
Marsa Bareika	27° 46' 59 "N ,34° 13' 0 "E	25
Marsa Ghozlani	27° 49' 15 "N ,34° 15' 9 "E	25
Ras Burg	27° 45' 22 "N ,34° 15' 9 "E	30
Ras Ghozlani	27° 47' 31 "N ,34° 15' 45 "E	30
Ras Za'atar	27° 45' 51 "N ,34° 15' 21 "E	15
Shark & Yolanda Reef	27° 43' 30 "N ,34° 15' 33 "E	30
Shark Observatory	27° 44' 0 "N ,34° 15' 36 "E	30
The Key's	27° 44' 1 "N ,34° 14' 5 "E	25
The Light House	27° 43' 11 "N ,34° 14' 35 "E	30
Tiran Straits		
Gordon Reef	27° 59' 5 "N ,34° 27' 15 "E	50
Jackson Reef	28° 0' 21 "N ,34° 28' 16 "E	50
Kormoran	28° 1' 3 "N ,34° 29' 14 "E	12
North Laguna	28° 0' 21 "N ,34° 29' 5 "E	15
South Laguna Reef	27° 59' 50 "N ,34° 28' 54 "E	19
Thomas Reef	27° 59' 26 "N ,34° 27' 38 "E	25
Woodhouse Reef	28° 0' 7 "N ,34° 27' 58 "E	30

Figure 3. Entrance of the diving centre in Sharm-el-Sheikh.

For technical diving, the centre has three very experienced full-time Tec and Rebreather instructors. They run courses for ANDI, IANTD, SSI, TDI and PADI TecRec, which are different diving agencies. The tec instructors are certified full trimix on Defender, Poseidon Se7en, ISC Megalodon, ISC Pathfinder, APD Evolution, JJ-CCR, Hollis Prism 2, and SF-2, making a great choice for rebreather divers. In this case, CCR scientific divers (Closed-circuit rebreather) need to take their own rebreather. The centre will provide Diluent and Oxygen tanks (DIN exits) as well as the bailouts (DIN exits). The detailed list of the equipment to bring is provided later in the document. The centre has to comply with the standard guidelines provided by the CDWS which can be found on their website (<https://www.cdws.travel/>). In addition, according to the CDWS Board Members' decree #3/13/696, it is stated that the ratio of the diving guides/instructors to practitioners should be one guide/instructor to 12 practitioners for diving activities performed on safari or daily boats, this ratio aims to ensure a high level of safety standards.

For technical diving hosted by a recreational diving operator, the operator must employ a qualified technical diving instructor during the period of technical diving. He must be qualified up to the max operating depth of the client's diving activities. This experience does not have to be with the exact type of rebreather used by clients when diving CCR. The instructor must be certified by a recognized training agency and obtain a CDWS professional card. The technical divers are responsible for creating, renewing and verifying their dive plans, gas blends checks and verification. The tech instructor must verify safety procedures of all the technical dive activities performed by the clients. All proper documents and forms must be prepared and used, such as diver's registration, liability release and medical statement, and tanks and gas mixtures log. The safety briefing must include local area rules, regulations and hazards, the max depth allowed for each level, the allowed and restricted/forbidden diving activities, and any other rules set by the dive centre or local regulations. Finally, all gas blends must be prepared by a certified gas blender or purchased from a certified gas blending centre/filling station.

In Egypt, the CDWS defines the depth limitations according to the certifications. It is implementing the World Recreational Scuba Training Council (WRSTC) standards for recreational diving. As such, the

maximum depth for diving with **compressed air** is **40 metres** (if certifications of the diver allow it). For air diving, the maximum depth is up to a partial pressure of oxygen (PPO₂) of **1.4 ATA** (= 40 m). For technical activities, the maximum PPO₂ for bottom mix is **1.4 ATA** and the maximum PPO₂ for decompression mix is **1.6 ATA**. Depth limitations for technical activities are the following:

Deco Procedures	45 m
Extended Ranges	55 m
Normoxic Trimix	60 m
Hypoxic Trimix	100 m

It is important to note that CDWS does not recommend nor support any recreational technical diving activities deeper than the depths mentioned above; meaning that they are not forbidden. In this case, for any technical dives deeper than the depths mentioned above (extreme and/or records) – using open circuits or closed-circuit rebreathers – the divers and the technical manager of the Diving center are fully responsible for their activities, their own and other participants' safety. Additionally, the divers should consider that their rebreather is CE (European Conformity, the design and construction must follow the EN 14143) for the planned depth: for instance, JJ-CCR is CE until 100 m depth.

By all means the following must be prepared, reviewed and approved by the Technical manager of the operation prior to the dive date:

1. Divers training qualifications
2. Proof of diving experience
3. The dive plan and the dive gas mixes
4. The dive location
5. Proof of support team's training qualifications
6. List of emergency equipment at the site and the emergency plan
7. Proof of dive insurance covering the team to planned maximum depth

In addition, first aid box content for daily boats (point 4 of the Equipment section above) and recreational technical diving Centers Requirements and Standards can be found online following the link <https://www.cdws.travel/rules-regulations>.

6. Administrative requirements

All members of the dive team will be in possession of a mission order signed by their employer's delegate before the start of the training/mission. This mission order will stipulate the date of the mission, the area to be studied and the purpose of the mission and methods to be applied. It will clearly state that the dive team member will be involved in scientific diving activities, and that all insurance arrangements have been made.

In complement, each diver should have passed a general medical examination directed by a physician stating that the diver has no contraindication for diving activities and that the diver has been deemed fit for diving in accordance with Article 15 of the Royal Decree 28/04/2017 for belgian workers; or a medical certification according to the law of country of origin of the visiting scientific diver. This medical certificate should not be older than one year before the last day of the expedition.

They will also have diving insurance on top of their employer's one, and have a first care certification still valid (less than 2 years).

Each diver should be in possession of a valid scientific diving licence delivered and recognized by the national authority, as well as a proper certification for CCR hypoxic trimix diving in this particular case.

7. Scientific diving team

Members of a scientific diving team have to comply with administrative rules related to occupational diving organised by Belgium authorities, as stated previously. Those are the following:

- 1) A valid scientific diving licence delivered recognized by the national authority;
- 2) A mission order delivered by the employer confirming that scientific diving will be part of the worker activities during the whole duration of the mission;
- 3) A valid medical certificate confirming that the worker is able to perform scientific diving activities;
- 4) A diving insurance on top of the employer's insurance for bodily injury coverage related to scientific diving activities.

Those considerations are mandatory. Then, more specifically, to perform the tasks of this project, the diving team need to include divers which are:

>Certified with advanced trimix CCR (no matter the unit)

>Have a strong experience in deep dives with long decompression procedures

>Have experience of dive in open sea from a boat with currents and heavy gear configuration

It is important that the divers are in a good physical and mental state (in addition to the valid medical certification) to handle underwater tasks at greater depths with long decompression procedures. With such deep and long dives, it is important that the divers have respectful behaviour, avoid overconfidence in their own capacities, and are rigorous with the preparation of the dives.

The dives planned will not be adequate for deep diving training nor to fine tune the gear configuration, therefore it is important that each diver knows his own equipment, although the first day of diving will be AIR diluent (shallow dives <40 m) dives in order to check gear configuration.

In accordance with this, all divers involved in this project (see the list below) have been trained according to the standards from the host country of their research institution. Besides their diving skills, all the divers are able to contribute to the scientific manipulations required to accomplish the objectives. All divers have a strong experience of CCR diving and long decompression procedures (>2H30). All divers will have received proper and specific training according to the working conditions and the work to be performed, as required by Article 14 of the Royal Decree 28/04/2017.

Diving team from Belgium:

- 1) Dr. Alain NORRO

Affiliation: Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences

Employer: Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences

Roles: ABSD Instructor, CCR instructor full trimix

- 2) Dr. Lucas TERRANA

Affiliation: Natural History Museum & Vivarium of Tournai / Université Libre de Bruxelles

Employer: City of Tournai

Roles: ABSD Candidate, advanced trimix ccr diver (JJ-CCR)

Local diver:

1) Andrew Auckland

Affiliation: Infinite CCR

Employer: Infinite CCR hosted by Circle Diving

Roles: IANTD and TDI instructor of various specialities, including full cave and full trimix rebreather, thousands of dives of experience

8. Gas availability, quality & planning

During all the week, the divers will benefit from gas filling by certified technicians of the dive centre and therefore will not manage their fillings themselves. However, it is their responsibility to choose the proper gas composition (diluent and bailouts) according to the dive planned, and to analyse them prior to use. Gas filling has to be done following rules dictated by the CDWS for which the dive centre has to strictly comply (these can be consulted following <https://www.cdws.travel/rules-regulations>, document "Filling Station Standard"). Divers will have helium and oxygen available for their mixes. To comply with the Belgian Royal Decree (A.R. 23/12/2003, Art.5, 4°, Annex 1), the quality of the gas should be regularly tested and should:

- Not exceed 10 (500 ppm as for EN12021) hectopascals in partial pressure of carbon dioxide (CO₂);
- Not exceed 0.05 hectopascals in partial pressure of carbon monoxide (CO);
- Not have a partial pressure of oxygen inferior to 200 hectopascals, and not exceed 1900 hectopascals;
- Not exceed 5 mg/m³ in oil vapor concentration (less than 0.1 mg/m³ for oxygen compatible gear);
- Not exceed 50 mg/m³ in water vapor (@200b EN12021);
- Not present any odour, any dust, any oxide or metal particles, nor toxic or irritating substances.

Concentrations have to be measured in atmospheric pressure and comply with these values. Such tests can be performed with commercial kits (Kitagawa™ analysis & control kit). Should any potentially hazardous compound see its level rise above the values specified by the EU 12021 norm, the dive centre should be advised and proper service of the compressor done.

Each gas used and analysed by the diver should be properly labelled with maximum operating depth, initials of the analyser, date, pressure, and mix.

The dive centre will also provide soda lime for the scrubber of their rebreathers. Divers should take care to follow the rules of their manufacturer. For instance, JJ-CCR recommends only the soda lime Sofnolime® 797 manufactured by Molecular Products, but other brands might work as well. They advise a running time of 180 min on the axial scrubber (~2.5 kg) and mention that a dive should not be done with soda lime that has already been used. In practice, a recent study has shown that a partially used scrubber canister can be used the next day without any special procedure to store the soda lime, as it is unlikely to influence the

scrubber efficiency (Pollock *et al.* 2018³). Therefore, several dives can be made with the same scrubber as long as it does not exceed the running time recommended by the manufacturer. However, any trimix dive (deeper than 40m) should be started with new soda lime for security purposes.

The divers should also take care to change their O₂ cells according to the manufacturer's rules. For instance, the JJ-CCR has three O₂ cells (type R17, galvanic, output 9-13 mV) with a given shelf life of 3 months and a maximum operating time of 12 months after installation. Calibration of the cells with pure oxygen should be done at atmospheric pressure following the manufacturer's rules. Some other units may ask for a 2-point calibration with air as well.

Gas planification (*i.e.* gas composition and volume) should be done according to the planned depth and runtime of the dive. Following local rules, air can be used until 40m depth, normoxic trimix until 60m depth, and hypoxic trimix until 100 m depth. Software such as MultiDeco can be used to prepare dives and determine best mixes.

Diluent mixes

In the case of this project, all the participants have the hypoxic certification. It is then suggested to use heliair mixes for both normoxic and hypoxic dives as they are easy to prepare (add helium, then top up with air), and have good parameters. The Equivalent Narcotic Depth should stay between 30-35 m, density not exceed 6.3 g/L, and PPO₂ not exceed 1.1 bar at maximum depth. Following these considerations, heliair are chosen:

- For a normoxic dive (max. 60m),
100 bar AIR + 100 bar He = 200 bars of **10/50** diluent
At 60 m, this diluent would have the following parameters:
 - PPO₂ of 0.7 bar
 - Density of 5.18 g/L with a setpoint at 1.3
 - END of 25 m.
- For a hypoxic dive (max. 100m),
50 bar AIR + 150 bar He = 200 bars of **5/75** diluent
At 100 m, this diluent would have the following parameters:
 - PPO₂ of 0.55 bar
 - Density of 5.35 g/L with a setpoint at 1.3
 - END of 18 m.

With these mixes, the narcosis due to nitrogen is strongly limited. In case of hyperoxia at depth, the rinse will be efficient with the diluent PPO₂ values (see next chapters for details). In these calculations, the Oxygen is not considered narcotic, as done by TDI and IANTD. Other agencies such as CMAS, GUE and PADI do consider oxygen as narcotic.

³ Pollock, N. W., Gant, N., Harvey, D., Mesley, P., Hart, J., & Mitchell, S. J. (2018). Storage of partly used closed-circuit rebreather carbon dioxide absorbent canisters. *Diving and Hyperbaric Medicine*, 48(2), 96.

Bailouts

Bailouts are normally used in case of emergency when the divers need to surface after a problem that he cannot solve underwater on his machine (see next chapters for details). It is likely that the dive centre will provide bailouts already filled with a mix, and most likely the divers will not choose their gas for bailouts. In addition, bailout gas volume has to be calculated based on the planned depth and the maximum runtime authorised, which is often imposed by the captain/the dive centre (this time is also often decided depending on the presence of other divers on the boat and their level); but also on the breathing rate. To cover stress situations, respiratory minute volume is set to 20 L/min for gas calculations (taking into account that the RMV of the three divers is around 12-15 L/min). Dive planification should be done in accordance with the gas provided once there, but also on Gradient Factors of the divers that may influence total ascent time.

Typical steps would be:

1. Calculate available bailout gas
2. Calculate your gas requirements for bailout ascent (including deco times)
3. Compare these gas requirements against available gas
 - Then three choices
 - Reduce bottom time within gas limits or
 - Carry (stage if guaranteed access) extra gas
 - Mutualise gas to ascend 1.5 divers (IANTD rule)
4. Using tables or dive planning software, plan a bailout ascent within gas restraints and identify the maximum bailout time you can get out of that gas.
5. Decide on “other factors” and known personal limits what the maximum tolerable ascent time can be in the event of the bailout, this may reduce the time

When diving, it is unlikely to stay at the same bottom depth the whole time, but it would be the case for scientific diving when accomplishing a scientific task (for instance sediment coring), or exploring a wreck for example. In any case, one important parameter to consider is the maximum Time to Surface (TTS) that can be managed using the available bailout gas, including the reserve. This TTS should also consider the scrubber and onboard gas duration limits to be calculated. Max TTS can be calculated with the required bailout ascent/deco time and bailout gas for determined stops, using defined consumption rates. Everything can be calculated with softwares, and then the total runtime less the bottom time in the plan will give the TTS that we can reach during the dive.

Bailout mixes should be chosen to switch to open circuit at maximum operating depths with a PPO₂ of ~1.6 bar to optimise decompression. The choice of gas mixes should be done in order to keep a minimal PPO₂ between 0.6-0.8 bar at the depth of the gas switch, as the partial pressure will quickly drop during the ascent. It is also important to mention that gas switches have to minimise isobaric counter-diffusion between Helium and Nitrogen and should be chosen in order to minimise large differences in partial pressures. Still, there is no fixed rule for gas switches. Doolette and Mitchell (2003)⁴ propose a more practical approach: minimising

⁴ Doolette, D. J., & Mitchell, S. J. (2003). Biophysical basis for inner ear decompression sickness. *Journal of Applied Physiology*, 94(6), 2145-2150.

the switch from trimix to nitrox on ascent or planning to perform these switches at depth or in shallow water to minimise supersaturation.

For trimix dives, the divers mutualise the gas within the team. For hypoxic dives, every diver should carry his own bottom gas, and then share travel and deco mixes. Bailouts should be fully used or not: therefore, it is advised to only take 20 bars for the reserve (gauge error). It should be noted that Central Nervous System (CNS) values would exceed 100% with long and deep dives, but it would not be problematic. Triox (oxygen and helium) might be used as long as PPO₂ at depth, END and MOD fit the plan.

9. Decompression procedure

During the ABSD training, it is planned to perform 2 dives with Air diluent, 3 normoxic dives, and one hypoxic dive. Gas planification will be made (see above) prior to the dive and the decompression procedure will entirely depend on which gas is available for bailout, for diluent and which volume is taken by the divers, or if there is a surface support for oxygen or not, which might not be the case.

In a general way, the setpoint high of the rebreathers is 1.2 or 1.3 bar in PPO₂. Electronic rebreathers should pass the high setpoint once at depth, because if it is passed before, during the descend phase, the PPO₂ will increase quickly and there will be a risk of hyperoxia. For instance, JJ-CCR operates on 1.3 (even though it is modifiable by the diver). This is the PPO₂ that will be breathed at depth during the dive. Once at 6m, an oxygen flush is advised and PPO₂ should reach more than 1.5 (almost never 1.6 due to water condensation in the loop). It is advised to stay at minimum 1.4 during the decompression.

Gradient Factors are personal and no value can be imposed on the divers. Generally, for air diluent dives the GF are set at 80/80 or 85/85. There is no need to decrease the low gradient factors when diving air as it will influence the depth of the first deco stops, and when diving with high loads of nitrogen (i.e. air) we do not want to stay at depth during deco phase. For normoxic trimix, common GF are 50/80 while for hypoxic trimix lots of divers use 30/70, but again this is personal and it should consider the diver's experience, and physiological state. However, it would be advised to use small low gradient factors when breathing helium, even though on normoxic trimix dives there is a recent increase in divers setting their GF in 80/80⁵.

As discussed in the previous chapter about gas planification, gas mixes for bailouts should be calculated to minimise isobaric counter-diffusion between helium and nitrogen during gas switches. The partial pressure of nitrogen should also be kept minimal to minimise the effects of narcosis (=END, with minimum values which are depending on the training agency, but it is advised to have an END around 30 m to 35m, corresponding to ~3.2 to ~3.5 bar of PPN₂).

Dive team should stay together during the complete dive including the decompression phase. Therefore, if the two divers do not have the same GF configuration, the general rule is that one of them should comply with the most restrictive plan and follow the plan to keep the team together. However in the Red Sea, with the good visibility (+15m) and dropoff ascent, a small delay between the divers can be accepted (to be defined

⁵ De Ridder S, Pattyn N, Neyt X, Germonpré P. Selecting optimal air diving gradient factors for Belgian military divers: more conservative settings are not necessarily safer. *Diving Hyperb Med.* 2023 Sep 30;53(3):251-258. doi: 10.28920/dhm53.3.251-258. PMID: 37718300.

in advance). The decompression plan will be planned at least the day before the dive, using software such as MultiDeco which allows divers to play with all parameters. There are several algorithms for decompression procedure, but one of the most commonly used now is the ZHL-16C algorithm, which the one used on the Shearwater computers for instance that are connected to some rebreathers such as the JJ (they can also stand the VPM-B model upon charged software update).

The deco plan can be written on a slate, with deco stops and depths, but the most important thing to keep in mind is the TTS (total time to surface) which will dictate the end of the dive, among other parameters (scientific task accomplished, incident, etc.). Writing the plan on a slate has the disadvantage of forcing the divers to keep a strict square dive plan. It is advised to carry a back-up computer allowing the CCR/OC mode with the choice of GF. This backup computer will stay at a high setpoint slightly lower than the setpoint of the CCR (1.2/1.25 instead of 1.3 for instance) for safety purposes, as the low setpoint phase (descend) can be neglected for the deco calculation.

The final phase of the decompression can be made between 3 and 6m. Some divers make all their stops at 6m. This has to be chosen between both the divers prior to the dive. Whatever the depth of the final stop, the divers should take care to have a very slow ascent during the last phase of the decompression, from 6m to the surface. It is advised to reduce the speed of ascent to 1 m/min during the last 6 metres. During this phase, divers can make oxygen flush to raise PPO₂. In deep and long dives it is very common to go far beyond the 100% CNS value (proxy of oxygen effect on the Central Nervous System) without any problem, due to the duration of the dive.

When bottom time is reached, or the scientific task accomplished, all the divers should shoot their red/orange SMB to the surface to signal that they start their ascent and decompression procedure. For this purpose, the divers should carry a reel of at least 130m. The ascent speed until 6m should not exceed 12 m/min. If any problem should arise, each diver has his own yellow SMB attached to an independent spool of at least 30m that they can shoot to the surface.

For each dive, gas analyses, mixes, volumes, pressures, deco plan and dive parameters will be registered on the "General Register" following Belgian Royal Decree of 28/04/2017 (see below).

ABSD Training - GENERAL REGISTER

Sharm el-Sheikh, Egypt - 2023
 Dr. Lucas Terrana - ABSD candidate - lucas.terrana@tournai.be
 Natural History Museum & Vivarium of Tournai

Dive Report n°	Site	Max depth	Dive Center Contact details Circle Divers Address Ras Umm Sid, Badawia Hotel, Al Ferouseya, South Sinai Governorate 46619 Phone +201022180946
Date	Longitude	Max runtime	
Place	Latitude	Type of dive CCR / OC	
Tasks planned and gear used			

Departure from	Vessel / RIB / Shore	Successive dive	yes/no	Time out 1st dive
Estimated return time				Surface interval

GAS PLANIFICATION

GAS PLAN - DIVER 1 - NAME.....SURNAME.....ROLE.....								
	Tank	Pressure	Total volume	Gas	MOD	Max PpO2	Max density (20°C)	Analyzed by
Diluent CCR	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
Oxygen CCR	L	bar	L	100%	6 m	1.6 bar	2.09 g/L	
OC bottom	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
OC travel	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
OC deco	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	

GAS PLAN - DIVER 2 - NAME.....SURNAME.....ROLE.....								
	Tank	Pressure	Total volume	Gas	MOD	Max PpO2	Max density (20°C)	Analyzed by
Diluent CCR	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
Oxygen CCR	L	bar	L	100%	6 m	1.6 bar	2.09 g/L	
OC bottom	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
OC travel	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
OC deco	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	

GAS PLAN - DIVER 3 - NAME.....SURNAME.....ROLE.....								
	Tank	Pressure	Total volume	Gas	MOD	Max PpO2	Max density (20°C)	Analyzed by
Diluent CCR	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
Oxygen CCR	L	bar	L	100%	6 m	1.6 bar	2.09 g/L	
OC bottom	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
OC travel	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
OC deco	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	

Depth limit for normoxic dives: 60 m - hypoxic dives : 100 m -- Diluent: max. ppO2 1.1 bar -- Bailouts: max. PpO2 bottom 1.4 bar - deco 1.6 bar -- Max. gas density should not exceed 6.3 g/L

Sodalime type						
	Used time	Depth and t° last dive	Remaining time	Used time	Depth and t° last dive	Remaining time
Diver 1				Diver 3		
Diver 2				Diver 4		

ABSD Training - GENERAL REGISTER

Sharm el-Sheikh, Egypt - 2023
 Dr. Lucas Terrana - ABSD candidate - lucas.terrana@tournai.be
 Natural History Museum & Vivarium of Tournai

GAS PLAN - DIVER 4 - NAME.....SURNAME.....ROLE.....								
	Tank	Pressure	Total volume	Gas	MOD	Max PpO2	Max density (20°C)	Analyzed by
Diluent CCR	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
Oxygen CCR	L	bar	L	100%	6 m	1.6 bar	2.09 g/L	
OC bottom	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
OC travel	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	
OC deco	L	bar	L		m	bar	g/L	

DIVE PLAN

Planned depth	<input type="text"/>	Max. Runtime authorized	<input type="text"/>	Planned BT	<input type="text"/>	Planned runtime	<input type="text"/>
Diver 1	GF / <input type="text"/>	Max. bottom time	<input type="text"/>	Planned TTS	<input type="text"/>		
Diver 2	GF / <input type="text"/>	Max. bottom time	<input type="text"/>	SAC rate bottom travel	<input type="text"/>	SAC rate deco	<input type="text"/>
Diver 3	GF / <input type="text"/>	Max. bottom time	<input type="text"/>	Bottom gas necessary for 1 diver	<input type="text"/>	available:	<input type="text"/> for <input type="text"/> divers
Diver 4	GF / <input type="text"/>	Max. bottom time	<input type="text"/>	Travel gas necessary for 1 diver	<input type="text"/>	available:	<input type="text"/> for <input type="text"/> divers
				Deco gas necessary for 1 diver	<input type="text"/>	available:	<input type="text"/> for <input type="text"/> divers

DIVE LOG

Max. depth	<input type="text"/>	Current	<input type="text"/>	CCR pre-dive checklist Diver 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Diver 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Diver 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Diver 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	Blank space for calculations
Runtime	<input type="text"/>	Wind	<input type="text"/>		
Deco time	<input type="text"/>	Swell	<input type="text"/>		
Time in	<input type="text"/>	Visibility	<input type="text"/>		
Time out	<input type="text"/>	Incident	<input type="text"/>		
Temp. °C	<input type="text"/>	Accident	<input type="text"/>		

REMARKS

Signatures - By signing the participant approves the diving plan

Dive leader

Divers

Skipper

10. Operational Risk Management

10.1 General procedures

All the dive missions are performed in sea water; the daily boat serves as platform for these dives. The boat is only operated by the staff and nobody from the scientific and diving team will be in charge of it. Following the general briefing the day before and then confirmed in the morning with the diving centre staff, the dive plan and decompression procedures can be arranged. Prior to each dive, the dive centre staff will give a briefing about the site, the topography, depth, fauna & flora, and other specificities like current, turbidity, caves, wrecks, etc. . .

The work will be accommodated to allow the completion of the envisioned dive tasks considering the weather and sea conditions. Even though repetitive dives will be allowed and planned, there will always be at least 2 hours between immersions with air diluent, with a maximum of two dives performed per diver and per day. For trimix dives, it will be limited to once a day. Moreover, as it is standard procedure, an off-gassing day will be observed for each diver after five consecutive days of diving. Additionally, the divers will be required to have good uninterrupted sleep, and to maintain a good level of hydration prior the start and throughout the whole week. Alcohol consumption will be forbidden between repetitive dives, and of course before any dive. It is recommended to avoid alcohol consumption for the entire period.

Normal working hours are not applicable in light of the limited time of the cruise, and due to the extra diving-related working time needed to maintain CCRs and prepare the scientific material needed for the tasks. The dive leader will also work extra time to record and document all the diving activities of the day on a pre-printed logbook (the register, with full details on the site, tasks, profiles and divers) and on diver's personal files (each/diver with personal record of their diving activities, which will be countersigned by the Dive Leader in accordance to Article 9 to 12 of the Royal Decree 28/04/2017).

As required by Article 13 of the Royal Decree 28/04/2017, this activity register will include the following information:

- 1) Identification of the employer;
- 2) The date, duration and location of the work;
- 3) The nature of the work and the work equipment to be used;
- 4) The name and function of all workers involved on site during the work;
- 5) The composition of breathing gases;
- 6) Pressure at time of exposure;
- 7) The address of the hospital or institution where emergency care can be administered;
- 8) Any accident or incident that occurred during the work;
- 9) The address of the decompression chamber.

The Operational Risk Management should be reviewed with all the dive team and questions will be answered, if any. Divers are supposed to keep a good training level throughout the year prior to departure. This means at least 12 dives in the last year including 6 with a scientific task at work.

All diving sites are touristic places well documented. There will not be any new unexplored site. Conditions such as current and visibility will be estimated prior to each diving activity by the crew of the dive centre.

Every day, safety procedures, expected/identified risk and mitigation measures, and dive plans are reminded. Generally speaking, the dive leader will make sure to organise the dive team in such a fashion that the dive tasks will be planned accounting for individual skills and physical fitness. This means that if any diver feels that his/her physical or mental capacities are not in line with one or several of the foreseen tasks, he/she won't be asked to take part in them. No solo dive is expected.

In general, water entry will be made from the support boat

In any situation, the dive leader, the expedition leader and/or the skipper can decide not to allow a diver to enter the water and that without notice if deemed necessary for safety reasons. Similarly, all dives are conducted by free will from the divers, who can abort/call a dive at any point without notice and explanation.

The dives will be performed using rebreathers. Therefore, it is the responsibility of each diver to complete the full checklist of his unit as advised by the manufacturer. Then, once on the boat and before the dive, after the dive briefing the team should go for a "GVI" check (Gas-Volume-Instruments) as a team to check that everybody is ready to dive.

10.2 Dive Mission Risks analysis

- First category: hazards linked to the usage of high-pressure gas and of diving equipment

- Risk n°1:

Use of high-pressure compressor and booster

- ✓ Control n°1:

Only authorised personnel from the dive centre will operate the compressor. The compressor itself fulfils all local relevant legislation and safety control or national legislation of the diving team in case no local legislation exists. The compressor should be serviced following the manufacturer's rules.

- Risk n°2:

Use of high-pressure diving tanks

- ✓ Control n°2:

All tanks used during this mission should follow the Egyptian law (see before), i.e. a pressure test & visual inspection every 5 years and in alternance every year a visual inspection. These tests are stamped in the upper side of each tank⁶.

⁶ R YYYY/MM + stamp of the authorised testing company for pressure test and RR YYYY/MM + stamp of the

- Risk n°3:

Pollution of the breathing gas

- ✓ Control n°3:

Following Belgian legislation, the quality of the air/mixes output from the compressor is permanently checked against EU 12021 norm (using commercial kit such as Kitagawa™ analysis & control kit). A copy of the service documentation should be displayed by the dive centre to the Scientific Dive Leader to be added to the final Diving Activities Report.

- Risk n°4:

Personal diving equipment loss or damage

- ✓ Control n°4:

Apart from tanks (diluent, oxygen and bailouts), divers will arrange with their staff the use of personal diving gears. In case of loss or damage to the equipment, the employer insurance will arrange the replacement of the lost item(s) by identical/similar equipment as requested by the diver, and assume the cost of this replacement.

- Risk n°5:

Faulty/malfunctioning equipment (drysuit, regulators, etc...)

- ✓ Control n°5:

All divers will make sure to bring equipment in perfect conditions, to have regulators and drysuits serviced by competent personnel before the mission starts and test it during test dives before packing it for the cruise. Proof of servicing should be available to the Scientific Dive Leader upon request before the start of the training. If any problem appears, it is the responsibility of every diver to fix it before departure. Moreover, it is advisable that each diver carries with him one spare for every sensitive equipment used (e.g. two sets of masks, one backup computer, spare fin straps). Additionally, for less common type of failures, a spare kit will be put together for the benefit of all the members of the diving team (e.g. spare drysuit inflator/purge, spare swivel for a pressure gauge, neoprene glue and neoprene bands in case of tearing from a neck seal, set of standards o-rings for regulators, ...).

- Second category: hazards linked to boat and boat operation

- Risk n°6:

Working in a slippery zone

✓ Control n°6:

Drainage on the floor of the boat ensures elimination of the water. Wipers will be available and should be used when needed. The deck is coated in non-skid/non-slip painted surface, nevertheless extra caution is requested by all the crew members and proper shoes will be compulsory when working on deck and not equipped for diving. Moreover, divers will be instructed to take special care when moving around heavy gear.

• Risk n°7:

Wrong handling of the boat, missing safety equipment, breakdown

✓ Control n°7:

Only competent personnel from the dive centre will handle the boat. The safety equipment will be regularly checked (e.g charging the mobile transceivers prior any trip), as well as other equipment of the boat (e.g. presence and integrity of the anchor & anchor rope with a length adapted to the site, availability of two back-up paddles).

Third category: hazards linked to the diving operations

• Risk n°8:

Strong currents that could make the dive difficult or the divers drifting

✓ Control n°8:

Local crew will make sure to analyse weather conditions prior to any dive, and they will have the final decision. If weather conditions of the previous days result in strong waves at a given dive site, this site is not visited that day or a new evaluation of the conditions on site is carried out. For this estimation both the safety of the diver as well as the feasibility of a diver recovery and the safety of the boat personnel are considered.

• Risk n°9:

Third-party boats traffic (tourism, military or scientific) causing a collision with a diver

✓ Control n°9:

In the diving area, there might be a lot of traffic, as it is a very touristic area. An alpha flag will always be displayed on the mast of the boat when divers are in the water. In case of surfacing in another place than a shotline or a mooring, the divers should always shoot their SMB to signal their presence at the surface.

• Risk n°10:

Poor visibility in the water due to particles influx linked to summer freshwater runoffs

✓ Control n°10:

Reduced visibility does not generally compromise the work, especially as the members of the dive team will have been trained in confined Belgian waters where poor visibility is commonplace. If extreme cases of bad visibility are likely, for example during sediment coring, divers will be tethered and have a buddy line and

pay special attention to stay close during the underwater work. Moreover, all divers will carry a powerful dive light during all dives, and at least one spare lamp will be available by buddy team. In the Red Sea, it is unlikely that these conditions happen.

- **Risk n°11:**

Diving in polluted waters

- ✓ **Control n°11:**

The diving area is near touristic places with numerous hotels in Sharm-el-Sheikh, but some areas are National Parks. Therefore, contaminations are not expected. Nevertheless, divers will be equipped with drysuits/wetsuits and gloves, which will drastically reduce any exposure to any potential contaminant in the environment. If after a dive a contact with an unexpected contaminant is suspected (e.g., redness and irritation of the skin), divers will thoroughly rinse their face (only exposed part to the water) as soon as possible, and contact will be made with the physician of the expedition for a teleconsultation.

- **Risk n°12:**

Decompression sickness

- ✓ **Control n°12:**

The risk of decompression sickness is minimised by different manners.

1-Cold management

Diving will be made in ~25°C water, but for longer trimix dives all divers will make sure to wear proper suits and gloves to delay cold sensation.

2-Physiological state and post-dive behaviour

All divers will make sure to stay correctly hydrated during the whole expedition, have sufficient amounts of sleep, and eat well. Drinking alcohol will not be authorised when dives are planned. Smoking will be prohibited during the whole week? Additionally, an “off-gassing” day will be observed after having performed five consecutive days of diving. Finally, during all the briefing, all leaders will make sure that divers will dive with in mind “Safety first, Work second”, meaning that it is always better to leave a task unfinished than to push yourself at risk.

3-Static Planification

All dives will be rigorously planned based as stated in the “Decompression Procedures” chapter according to GF, diluent and bailout gas and volumes.

4-Dynamic Planification

As mentioned above, during the dive the TTS is monitored and is one of the signals to reach the surface. If during the dive one of the parameters should come close to the agreed threshold fixed during the planification, dive will be concluded and the ascent started.

- **Risk n°13:**

Out of gas situation

✓ Control n°13:

When diving with CCR, there are different scenarios where a tank can be empty. All divers are trained with their unit by certified agencies to face such risks and situations. In case of oxygen loss, diving should be aborted. Divers can surface using a nx80 or a 100% as off-board gas if available in the team, allowing them to complete their deco on the CCR without bailing out. If not available, they should bailout and abort the dive. If lost diluent, one bailout might be used as an off-board diluent considering the MOD to conclude the dive. If there is a lost bailout, and if the team does not have enough gas anymore, depending on the situation the dive should be aborted and one bailout might be used as diluent for semi-closed rebreather mode to finish the dive. This might happen if there is a total loss of electronics during the dive for instance.

• Risk n°14:

Hyperthermia of the divers prior the dive

✓ Control n°14:

The divers should protect themselves from sunburns and try to not be over warmed. They should stay away from direct sun, use proper clothes or sunscreen (harmless to corals), and stay hydrated (several litres per day).

• Risk n°15:

Entanglement in the environment

✓ Control n°15:

All divers will have been trained and have practised before the start of the training. They are trained to cut lines during an entanglement, and should carry at least two cutting tools, including one located in the safety triangle and therefore easily reachable.

• Fourth category: hazards linked to marine life

• Risk n°16:

Injuries/wounds due to marine life such as jellyfishes, corals, fireworms, fire corals, urchins...

✓ Control n°16:

The divers will have a good buoyancy control and trim in the water to avoid touching anything. Moreover, they will wear suits that will cover their body. Wearing gloves is also authorised by the CDWS. In case of sting, rinse the affected area with sea water, remove any spines from the skin with tweezers, soak in very warm water for at least 30 min and take painkillers.

• Risk n°17:

Bites by sharks, turtles or any other large animal

✓ Control n°17:

Divers should have responsible behaviour underwater and interpret correctly the animal's behaviours. They won't chase them, nor touch them or excessively approach them.

- Fifth category: hazards linked to scientific equipment

- Risk n°18:

Damage/loss of the equipment/samples during transportation to the boat, during transit to the dive site and during work

- ✓ Control n°18:

There will always be several people available for transportation from storage location to RIB and to handle the scientific equipment upon return from the field, meaning that no member of the team will be overloaded with equipment, avoiding the subsequent risk to drop sensitive gear/sample or to mishandling any piece of equipment. During transit with the RIB, all equipment will be secured to the handrail of the embarkation with the help of carabiners/hooks. When given to the divers, the sampling gear will be directly attached by the surface tender to the D-rings of the divers' equipment to avoid any drop, and inversely at the end of every dive.

- Risk n°19:

Entanglement with the 100kg lift bag used to retrieve lead weights, or uncontrolled ascent

- ✓ Control n°19:

There will never be any point of attachment between the diver and the working lift bag. If at any time the buoy starts ascending quickly, the diver should release everything even if the task was not accomplished and let it go alone to the surface.

- Risk n°20:

Injury due to the weights that have to be retrieved underwater

- ✓ Control n°20:

The weight can hurt the diver/damage the equipment underwater, therefore it will be handled cautiously. The diver will attach the belt with the weights to the lift bag by trying to not lift the belt to do so, but rather try to do it effortlessly, letting the belt on the ground if possible. Once at the surface, each weight will be removed from the belt (or BSD pockets) prior to moving them, to avoid handling heavy gear.

- Sixth category: hazards linked to CCR diving

- Risk n°21:

CO₂ hit – hypercapnia

✓ Control n°21:

Sodalime should be monitored, changed prior to any trimix dive and not exceed manufacturer's recommendations (for instance 3H for JJ-CCR with Sofnolime 797). Quality of the gas mix breathed should also be checked with its density.

• Risk n°22:

Hyperoxia

✓ Control n°22:

The valve of the O₂ tank should be checked for any damage prior to the dive, as well as the functioning of the MAV and the solenoid/nozzle. The O₂ cells should also be checked and calibrated, if they stay on a lower value than the setpoint, the solenoid would still inject oxygen (in the case of eCCR).

• Risk n°23:

Hypoxia

✓ Control n°23:

Pressure of the oxygen tank should be checked prior to the dive. The valve should be checked and open during the dive. If there is a solenoid/nozzle problem, injection should be done manually. If oxygen is lost, bailout or offboard with 80% (do not forget to make diluent rinse when hypoxia/hyperoxia).

• Risk n°24:

Boom Scenario

✓ Control n°24:

Close both diluent and oxygen valves. Then check manometers and act accordingly following procedures linked to the unit.

• Risk n°25:

Wrong gas

✓ Control n°25:

Each gas should be tested and labelled by the diver who is using them. Pressure should be checked as well. MOD should be clearly mentioned for bailout mixes. Generally, the bottom mix is worn at the left side, deco stages at the right side.

• Risk n°26:

PPO₂ cell values not coherent

✓ Control n°26:

Cell dates should be checked and changed if necessary. Computer should be calibrated with 100% oxygen at atmospheric pressure with the loop opened. If different values are given during the dive, make diluent flush to check which cells are not working and act accordingly following procedures made by the manufacturer and learnt during specific training.

• Risk n°27:

Leak of bubbles from the rebreather

✓ Control n°27:

Positive and negative tests should be done when preparing the unit. During immersion, make a stop at 5m to do a bubble check with the buddy. If bubbles appear during the dive, it should be discussed between the two divers. If small bubbles arise from the first stage, a hose, or the OPV, it might be handled until the end of the dive and then the unit could be checked afterwards. If the leak is too important, to not flood the unit the diver should bail out.

• Seventh category: hazards linked to the human factor

• Risk n°28:

Overtask load

✓ Control n°28:

The dive leader should take care to spread the scientific tasks throughout the week so it is not always the same diver that performs the main task while the buddy is the assistant underwater. He will also take care to listen to the needs and feelings of the divers by organising debriefings and let them give their debriefing as well.

• Risk n°29:

Overconfidence with its own capacities

Control n°29:

The Dive Leader will have chosen carefully his team to perform the task and to avoid such personalities. The dive leader spread the scientific tasks among the team to minimise the fact that it is always the same diver that performs the main task. Teams are configured in order that the diving teams have a turn-over.

• Risk n°30:

Worker feels exhausted, sick, or for any other reason does not want to dive

Control n°30:

All the team will always take care to stay hydrated and have a good sleep. However, if any diver does not want to dive because he does not feel good, safety will always be a priority before the scientific task. The

diver in bad condition will not perform the dive of the day and the task will be cancelled if there are not enough divers to perform it.

10.3 Mandatory equipment list

In accordance with article 6 of the Royal Decree of 28/04/2017, each diver's employer must ensure that the following personal safety equipment is made available to him or her, and arrange for any missing equipment to be purchased.

- Onboard

- 1) Lifejackets for non-divers.
- 2) Safety 15L tank with enriched gas (Nx80 or 100% O₂) with two regulators + safety line (at least 6m long) for its deployment.
- 3) Handheld GPS, AIS, navigation tools, etc...
- 4) DAN oxygen therapy kit with 5L oxygen bottle (200 bars).
- 5) Space blanket in case of signs of hypothermia.
- 6) First care case

- Diving equipment

- 1) Dry suit (+ spare or repair parts such as inflator, purge valve, sleeves...) and/or wetsuit
- 2) Boots, wet gloves or gloves according to the temperature or work situation
- 3) Thermic undergarment
- 4) Hood
- 5) Mask + spare mask
- 6) Full CCR including mouth-strap
- 7) Fins
- 8) Leads with belt and/or weight pockets if needed
- 9) Bailout regulators for at least two stages
- 10) Drysuit inflation regulator
- 11) One large orange SMB with a reel/spool (at least 30m) + one emergency yellow SMB already equipped on reel/spool (at least 30m) and ready to be deployed per diver in the water.
- 12) Line cutter and knife/scissors (x2).
- 13) Diving lamp
- 14) Compass
- 15) Wetnote
- 16) Backup dive computer with integrated CCR/OC
- 17) Double-enders
- 18) Spare kit for the diving team (exact content tbd).

10.4 Emergency plan

- Generalities

> All Belgian scientific diving operations are carried out following rules of the Royal Decree 28/04/2017 including the introduction of the divers to the operational risk management document that they will sign before the beginning of the expedition.

> Prior to every diving activity two briefings take place: one on the day before the diving takes place and one in the morning prior to the diving. Topics of this briefing are the aim of the dive, deco plan, gas choices, the description of the scientific task, and the procedure before/during/after the dive in terms of mobility & safety.

>The medical facilities are summarised in the Dive Register. There is a hyperbaric chamber in Sharm-el-Sheikh as well as an international hospital (Fig. 4):

-The hyperbaric chamber is located only ~8km (10-15 min drive by car) from the dive centre and the hotel.

Sharm el-Sheikh Hyperbaric Chamber and Medical Center

Located in Sharm el-Maya by the Travco Jetty

Telephone Number: (+20) 69-3660 922, 3

24hr Emergency numbers:

Dr. Adel Taher: (+20) 122 212 4292

Dr. Ahmed Sakr: (+20) 122 333 1325

-The international hospital is located only ~4km (5 min drive by car) from the dive centre and the hotel.

Sharm el-Sheikh International Hospital

Located at the International Hospital, Hi-El-Nor, El-Salam street

Telephone number: (+20) 69 3660 893, 5

24hr Emergency numbers:

Dr. Magdi Zakaria: (+20) 122 215 2196

Dr. Mohammed El Houfy: (+20) 69 3660 893, 5

Figure 4. Localisation of the medical facilities with regards to the hotel/dive centre.

- Medical emergency due to diving operations

At the beginning of the expedition, the safety procedure will be reviewed between all members of the team.

1) Problem underwater (gear failure, gas loss, ...)

Whatever the problem the divers encounter underwater (air loss, gear failure, scientific gear failure/loss, ...), they should shoot the yellow SMB to warn the surface safety that something is wrong. As the yellow SMB pops out of the surface, the skipper will directly navigate towards the divers and the deco-line with the spare tank (Nx80 or 100%) and regulator will be clipped on the SMB line and the deployed tank closed. In this case the divers will make their deco stop and then surface. If there was any excessive speed during the ascent, the primary diver in charge of leading the dive will decide to extend the safety stop for a few minutes. There is also the possibility to clip a slate on the yellow SMB to tell the surface support the nature of the problem.

2) Buddy loss

If the two divers lost themselves, each diver should look around them twice, check the water column above and below, and if there is no sight of the buddy, they should shoot their SMB and start their ascent. In this case, the surface safety will see both SMB and directly know that the divers are separated. In any case, each diver should respect their decompression plan prior to surfacing. The surface support may try to gather the SMB, so the divers can meet again underwater.

3) Problems related to the diver (decompression sickness or not) or decompression sickness suspicion

- Short of breath underwater (CO₂ hit)

The divers should stop any task/scientific activities, warn his/her buddy, stop and knee on the bottom if possible or grab a rock on a wall, make two diluent flush, and take the time to recover. If after a few breathing cycles the diver cannot recover, abort the dive. Air quality, soda lime and gas density are controlled during

the expedition to avoid such situations. Divers will take care to maintain a good physical state before and during the expedition as well.

-Injured diver still conscious

If a diver surfaces with an injury or any suspicion of decompression sickness (DCS); the boat will recover the divers onboard and directly bring them on the boat where the injury could be healed depending on the gravity. If the injury does not allow the diver to move by himself, then a safety member of the crew may jump on the water and give some help. If there was an ascent with excessive speed, then as safety precaution the divers will take oxygen for 30 min with an on-demand regulator first, as it provides the highest oxygen concentration without any waste, but if it does not feel comfortable at some point, the diver may ask the non-rebreather mask with oxygen set at 15L/min. If there is any suspicion of DCS (dizziness, extreme fatigue, skin itching, joint pain, ...), the diver should take 100% oxygen. The DAN emergency number (+39 0642115685) should be called and they will give instructions to follow.

Summary of barotrauma related to scuba-diving and methods to avoid them

They can occur when ascend speed is excessive, when there is no expiration during the ascent, when there is a shortness of breath, or in case of stress or panic with an uncontrolled ascend. In any case, ascending from depth should be done in a controlled speed, taking care to breath out properly. Barotraumas are:

Ears Take care not forcing Valsalva manoeuvre, do not use cotton buds to clean ears

Sinuses Do not dive if cold symptoms, nose clogged

Eye Expire with the nose in the mask when descending to the bottom

Teeth Keep a good buccal hygiene

Colic Abort dive

Lungs The most serious barotrauma that can lead to death. Expire during ascent

A. Pneumothorax

Symptoms: chest pain, difficulty to breath, blue skin, blood froth in the mouth, faint

B. Pneumomediastinum

Symptoms: crepitation in the chest

C. Emboly

Symptoms: intense chest pain

-Injured diver unconscious

If a diver is surfacing with his/her buddy unconscious, then all the safety loop will be deployed with the retrieval of the unconscious diver by the crew (with the help of the back-up diver or not) and then the basic life support will be given (CPR chain with oxygen therapy) following the procedures learnt with DAN trainings.

Simultaneously to the repatriation of the injured diver, the skipper will first evaluate all assets in the area and take contact with the nearest medical centres to warn that a medical evacuation might be needed.

During the repatriation, the following procedure must take place:

Free the diver of the equipment including the CCR and the mask directly at the surface before moving him onboard. Keep the diver protected from the wind/water/sun and try to keep the diver awake if conscious. If the diver is responsive, rescuers should try to ask the diver or his buddy what happened and ask details on the symptoms he feels (to be then collected onto the appropriate incident sheet). If the symptoms suggest a decompression incident or a lung overpressure injury, or if the diver is in a state of shock, administer

normobaric oxygen 100% at a constant flow of 15 L/min with the oxygen bottle connected to the non-rebreather mask. If unconscious, get the vitals. If the unconscious diver is not breathing carry out CPR, assisted with the oxygen tank connected to a bag valve mask:

NB: If a drowning is suspected, start first with 5 insufflations before starting CPR.

In the meantime, the crew will have contacted the nearest medical centre. If still unconscious, continue the CPR, and administer pure oxygen to the victim with a manually triggered ventilator.

>The closest hyperbaric chambers/hospital are directly at Sharm-el-Sheik (see evacuation form).

If the emergency is not related to diving *per se* or if it does not necessitate a recompression in a hyperbaric chamber, assess the seriousness of the injury, and decide with the skipper whether it can be treated onboard before an evacuation to a nearby facility is necessary.

Because the dives will be daily boat trips, the divers will never be too far from a medical centre.

During transfer to the medical facilities, the victim will stay in observation in a safe and comfortable place of the boat with at least one expedition member constantly at his side to ensure that his condition does not worsen. In the meantime, contact will be made with the insurer of the victim to coordinate a potential repatriation if necessary, and to arrange the necessary care that couldn't be provided on site. Additionally, the family of the victim will be warned as soon as possible from the incident, and will be kept updated about any significant development in the rescue effort or about any change in the patient status. ICE contact is mentioned by all the divers on a general medical document prior to the mission.

Summary of the Decompression Sickness

50% appears in the first 30 min post-dive

99% within 6 hours

100% 12–24 hours

1) Minor symptoms

- Extreme or unusual fatigue after the dive
- Unusual dizziness after the dive
- Skin itching

☑ 30 to 60 min with 100% oxygen

2) Major symptoms

- Anxiety, stress, fatigue
- Sensitivity loss
- Paralysis
- Blotches on skin
- Deafness
- Giddiness
- Vomiting

☑ 100% oxygen – hydration – emergency plan deployed, and DAN called

3) Type of sickness, from least serious to death danger:

A. Skin related: itch, blotch, swelling

B. Osteo-articular: bends (shoulders, kness, elbows)

C. Choke: DCS of the lung

D. Internal ear: dizziness, giddiness, vomiting, visual troubles, deafness

E. Neurological: Mono/hemiplegy, tetra/quadrupleg, not possible to speak anymore, coma, epilepsy, or medullary (spinal cord), difficulty to urinate, difficulty to move

11. Risk Mitigation after Risk Assessment

Risk identified	Severity	Risk control	Severity after control
Decompression sickness	High	Proper deco plan, gas choice, briefing, gear maintenance, good physiological state	Moderate
Entanglement with lift bag	High	Never be attached to the lift bag, good gear configuration	Moderate
Use of high-pressure compressor and booster	High	Used by competent staff and gear reglementation	Low
Use of high-pressure tanks	High	Maintenance and regular service following local rules	Low
Pollution of breathing gas	Moderate	Quality check on a regular basis	Low
Equipment loss or damage	Moderate	Equipment insured by employer, careness, redundancy	Low
Malfunctioning equipment	Moderate	Maintenance and service according to gear	Low
Slippery zone	Moderate	Caution and dry climate	Low
Wrong handling of the boat	Moderate	Crew following local rules for navigating and safety	Low
Strong currents	Moderate	Check meteo and tides, briefing before dive, SMBs	Low
Collision with other boats	High	Alpha flag, SMB	Low
Poor visibility	Low	Diving lights, stay close to buddy	Low
Polluted waters	Low	Wetsuit/drysuit, gloves, hood	Low
Out of gas	Moderate	Check gas pressure, trained divers, procedures during briefing, BO scenarios planned	Low
Hyperthermia	Moderate	Stay away from direct sun, good hydration	Low
Entanglement	Low	Two cutting tools carried by diver	Low
Injuries due to marine life	Low	Good trim, proper suit	Low
Bites by large animals	Moderate	Good behaviour, do not approach to close marine animals	Low
Damage/loss of equioment during transport	Low	Do not carry heavy gear without help, proper storage and use of equipment	Low
Injury with weights	Low	Handled cautiously, retrieve each weight and not entire belt/pocket	Low

CO2 Hit - Hypercapnia	Moderate	Change soda lime according to manufacturer's rules, CCR check prior to the dive, keep reasonable efforts underwater	Low
Hyperoxia	High	Check oxygen valve, MAV and solenoid function, check O2 cells and calibration, keep good PPO2 values for diluent and bailouts	Low
Hypoxia	High	Check oxygen valve, MAV and solenoid function, check O2 cells and calibration, keep good PPO2 values for diluent and bailouts	Low
BOOM Scenario	Moderate	Check leaks and dil/o2 pressures	Low
Wrong gas	High	Label and analyse tanks properly, good deco/BO plan prior to the dive, gas choices	Low
PPO2 cells not coherent	Moderate	Diluent check, check cell lifespan, change them according to manufacturer's rules	Low
Leak from CCR	Low	Bubble check at 5/6 m with buddy, good preparation prior to the dive with checklist, maintenance of the gear	Low
Overtask load	Moderate	Spread tasks, listen to divers' needs	Low
Overconfidence	Moderate	Dive leader constitutes his team, spread tasks, turn-over in teams	Low
Fatigue, sickness, diver do not want to dive	Moderate	Stay hydrated, good sleep, safety priority, dive cancelled if necessary	Low

END OF THE WORKING STATEMENT METHOD